

ISOP Consortium Members

Project Information

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Acronym: ISOP

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INNOVATION IN SUPERCRITICAL CARBON DIOXIDE POWER SYSTEMS (ISOP)

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INNOVATION IN SUPERCRITICAL CARBON DIOXIDE POWER SYSTEMS (ISOP)

Objective

The AIM of this four-year work programme is to undertake cutting edge multidisciplinary research and development to make a step change in understanding and advancing supercritical carbon dioxide (sCO₂) based power generation systems' technology. This will enable a step change in the role played by power and heat cycles to become major contributors to achieving the 2050 zero emissions targets. **ISOP** will achieve this goal while providing specialised training for 17 doctoral researchers to help to establish the backbone of an important industry.

Mission & Vision

From the considerations above, **ISOP** will, for the first time in the history of sCO₂ technology, gather twenty-two institutions together to advance the technology in order to resolve the key technical challenges that still stand out:

- i) integration of sCO₂-based power plants into different energy sources, since most R&D activities limit to major components and not Balance of Plant and auxiliaries (covered by **WP1**);
- ii) transient operation and controllability of sCO₂-based power plants, including fast/safe start-up/shutdown (covered by **WP2**);
- iii) enhanced performance of components not only in base load but also across the entire operating range (covered by **WP3**);
- iv) maturation of components through capital cost reduction and corrosion-life extension (covered by **WP4**).

ISOP is therefore a first-of-its-kind project since, for the first time, the most salient technology gaps of sCO₂ systems are tackled together in order to make great strides in the pathway to market deployment.

The fact that this is jointly carried out by a group of twenty-two institutions at the same time, working in a concerted manner, will boost the innovation potential in our continent in different areas: knowledge, new concepts for power generation and energy storage, operational features, modelling/simulation tools, new materials, coatings, component design, control.

Structure

The research programme is comprised of four closely related Work Packages (WPs) addressing different aspects of sCO₂ power cycles as identified in the technical objectives of the project.

- **WP1 - System Integration:**

The aim is to develop system integration concepts for sCO₂-based power generation systems exploiting different energy sources in either directly or indirectly heated configurations, as well as large-scale energy storage systems relying on sCO₂ power cycles. Additionally, advanced Artificial-Intelligence (AI) algorithms will be developed to identify the optimal integration of sCO₂ power systems for various applications and end-use scenarios, including carbon capture in directly fired systems, based on key performance Indicators of thermal, economic environmental and societal nature.

- **WP2 - System Operation, Transient Performance and Control:**

The objective is to gain an understanding of the requirements set for thermal power generation systems in a future decarbonised grid, in terms of operability and flexibility. Additionally, accurate prediction tools will be developed for the simulation of transient operation of sCO₂ power cycles, and innovative concepts for control and optimisation of operational strategies will be investigated using advanced digital and artificial intelligence techniques.

- **WP3 - Component Innovations, Turbomachinery and Heat Exchangers:**

The aim is to develop innovative methods to enhance aerodynamic and mechanical performance, reliability, and operability of key system components, namely turbomachinery and heat exchangers. This includes gaining an understanding of complex heat transfer phenomena occurring near the critical point, particularly those involving phase change, and characterizing the implications of extreme transient and stationary operating conditions on the aerodynamic, thermal, and mechanical performance of major equipment in sCO₂ power systems.

- **WP4 - Materials and Manufacturing:**

The goal is to understand the implications of extreme operating conditions on the material requirements of components in sCO₂ power systems. This includes exploring the potential utilization of non-metallic materials in sCO₂ power system components, understanding the effects of extreme operating conditions and working fluid composition on corrosion in sCO₂ power systems. Additionally, advanced modeling and experimental methods will be developed to enable the selection and development of materials, coatings, and manufacturing techniques for reliable and safer operation of key components in sCO₂ power cycles.

